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**CAREER MATURITY AMONG NINTH GRADE STUDENTS IN RELATIONSHIP TO
FAMILY CLIMATE**

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken with the purpose of studying career maturity of boys and girls of private and government school of ninth grade in relation to their family climate. A sample of 200 ninth grade students of Amritsar District was taken. The results indicate that: 1)no significant gender differences were found in career attitude 2) no significant gender differences were found in career competence 3)no significant type of school differences were found in career attitude4))no significant type of school differences were found in career competence5) significant relationship between career maturity (career competence& career competence) of boys and girls of ninth grade in relation to their family climatewas found.

The primary aim of education is to make an individual understand one's self and be able to decide upon one vocation or the other.The development of an individual through stages of maturity parallels the educational and vocational choice process. Career maturity is a measure of readiness to make career decisions on the basis of attitudes and knowledge of career decision making and assumes a great importance in the life of boys and girls of adolescent age for their proper future placement. The concept of career maturity was introduced by Super (1955) who called it vocational maturity and defined it conceptually as the place reached on the continuum of vocational development from exploration to decline. Thompson and Linderman (1981) defined

career maturity as the readiness to deal with career development tasks that are appropriate to one's stage in life.

The ability to look into the future and to think independently reflects personality factors which evolve from the family situations in which children are reared. Parental desires, their economic conditions, cultural atmosphere at home, the examples set by parents and the education of the parents play an important role in influencing the career choices of their children. Wiltfang and Scarbecz (1990) defined family climate as the characteristics determining the social status of the parents like educational level, occupational status and professions of the parents as well as the quality of the residence, working conditions of the parents and relations of the siblings. Greater the maturity, greater is the probability that the individual is able to make wise, sincere and satisfactory decisions with regard to career choices.

People who possess relatively high levels of career maturity are likely to obtain success and satisfaction in their careers because they display more awareness of the career decision-making process, often think about alternative careers, relate their present behavior to the future goals, possess high levels of self-reliance in making career decisions, are committed to making career choices, and are willing to acknowledge and concede to the demands of reality (Savickas, 1984). Greater career maturity and stronger support systems would significantly predict career decision-making, self-efficacy and vocational expectations of the individuals (Conkel-Ziebell, 2010).

Career maturity is influenced by age, race, ethnicity, locus of control, socio-economic status and gender. The complex interaction of these factors affects individual's readiness to succeed in mastering the task appropriate to various stage of career development. Although low income youth often have high aspirations, the influence of inadequate guidance and lack of information, high school preparation, or role model affects their 'fit' with career maturity model. Hall (2008) revealed that parental behaviors did relate to the career development of middle school students. The discrepancy between adolescents and parents views of family relationships are also related to the adolescents career decision-making self-efficacy. Mathur, Jain and saxena

(2010) revealed a significant difference between the vocational maturity of adolescents belonging to single parent families and intact family. Adolescents of intact families have better career maturity as compared to that of single parent families. It was also reported that the type of a family a person is brought up is an important determining factor regarding career maturity of an individual. Bacaroo (2011) revealed the gender differences, and found males more psychologically independent from their parents than females and females tended to choose social occupations with greater frequency than males. Only two dimensions namely goal selection and problem solving of career maturity competence show significant difference with favorable, moderate, and unfavorable types of family climate (Ranu & Kaur; 2012).

Hypotheses of the study

1. There exists no significant difference in career maturity (career attitude and career competence) of boys and girls of ninth grade.
2. There exists no significant difference in career maturity (career attitude and career competence) of ninth grade students studying in private and government schools.
3. There exists no significant correlation between career maturity (attitude and competence) and family climate of ninth grade students.

PROCEDURE OF THE STUDY

Methodology

In the present study, descriptive survey method was employed.

Sample

For the purpose of the study, 200 boys and girls from ninth class studying in private and government secondary schools of Amritsar district were selected.

Statistical Techniques Used

1. t -test were used to find the gender and type of school differences.
2. 'r' was calculated to find relationship between career maturity and family climate.

Tools used:

1. Indian adaptation of Career Maturity Inventory (CMI- Gupta, 1989).

2. Family Climate Scale(Shah, 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1 states, “There exists no significant difference in career maturity (career attitude and career competence) of boys and girls of ninth grade.”

In order to test this hypothesis, difference in the mean scores on the career attitude of boys and girls of ninth grade was calculated. Differences in the mean scores on career competence of boys and girls of ninth gradewere also calculated. The results are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Showing Difference in Mean Scores of Career Maturity (Attitude and Competence) of boys and girls of ninth grade.

Career Maturity	Boys			Girls			SE _d	t-value
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD		
Attitude Scale	100	28.14	5.827	100	27.80	4.966	0.77	0.44
Competence Scale	100	22.15	5.995	100	23.65	6.215	0.86	-1.733

Source: Field Survey, 2014

Discussion of Results:

Career Maturity (Attitude)

Table 1 depicts the values of Mean and SD of the scores of career attitude of boys and girls of ninth grade are 28.14 and 5.827 respectively and those of girls are 27.80 and 4.966 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 0.44, which is not significant at 0.05 level of confidence. It means that there exists no significant difference in career attitude of boys and girls of ninth grade.

Career Maturity (Competence)

Table 1 depicts the values of Mean and SD of the scores of competence of boys of ninth grade are 22.15 and 5.995 respectively and those of girls are 23.65 and 6.215 respectively. The t-value comes out to be -1.733, which is not significant at 0.05 level of confidence. It means that there does not exist significant difference in career competence of boys and girls of ninth grade.

On the basis of above discussion, it can be concluded that hypothesis no. 1 which states, “There exists no significant difference in career maturity (career attitude and career competence) of boys and girls of ninth grade”, is not rejected.

Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis 2 states, “There exists no significant difference in career maturity (career attitude and career competence) of students of ninth grade studying in private and government schools.”

In order to test this hypothesis, difference in the mean scores on the career attitude of adolescents studying in private and government schools were calculated. Difference in the mean scores on career maturity of students of ninth grade studying in private and government schools were also calculated. The results are presented in table 2

Table 2: Showing Difference in Mean Scores of Career Maturity (Attitude and Competence) of students studying in private and government Schools

Career Maturity	Private			Government			SE _D	t-value
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD		
Attitude Scale	100	28.75	4.856	100	27.12	5.898	0.76	2.159*
Competence Scale	100	22.45	5.994	100	23.33	6.281	0.87	-1.008

**significant at 0.05 level*

Discussion of Results

Career Maturity (Attitude)

Table 2 depicts the values of Mean and SD of career attitude of boys and girls of ninth grade studying in private schools are 28.75 and 4.856 respectively and those of boys and girls of ninth grade studying in government schools are 27.12 and 5.898 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 2.159, which is significant at both 0.05 confidence. It means that there exists a significant difference in career attitude of students of ninth grade studying in private and government schools.

Career Maturity (Competence)

Table 2 depicts the values of Mean and SD of boys and girls of ninth grade studying in private schools are 22.45 and 5.994 respectively and those of boys and girls of ninth grade studying in government schools are 23.33 and 6.281 respectively. The t-value comes out to be 1.008, which is not significant at 0.05 levels of confidence. It means that there does not exist a significant difference in career competence of boys and girls of ninth grade studying in private and government schools. This indicates that career competence of students studying in private schools is different than the students of government schools.

It is clear from the above discussion that career attitude shows a significant difference between students of ninth grade studying in private and government schools.

On the basis of above discussion, it can be concluded that hypothesis no. 2 which states, "There exists no significant difference in career maturity (career attitude and career competence) of boys and girls of ninth grade studying in private and government schools", is partially rejected.

Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis 3 states, "There exists no significant correlation between career maturity (attitude and competence) and family climate of ninth grade students."

To find out, correlation career maturity between career maturity and academic achievement of students of secondary schools matrix was prepared. The results were presented in table 3.

Table 3: Showing correlation between career maturity (Attitude Scale & Competence Scale) and family climate

Variables Career maturity	N	Value of 'r'
Attitude Scale and Family Climate	200	0.62
Competence Scale and Family Climate	200	0.70

Career Maturity (Attitude)

Table 3 shows that the value of correlation between attitudescale and family climate 0.62, which in comparison to table values was found significant.

Career Maturity (Competence)

Table 3 shows that the value of correlation between career competence scale and family climate is 0.70, which in comparison to table values was found significant.

It is clear from the above discussion that career maturity (attitude& competence) has significant relationship with family climate.

On the basis of above discussion, it can be concluded that hypothesis no. 3 which states, "There exists no significant correlation between career maturity (attitude and competence) and family climate of ninth grade students is rejected."

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

- Career orientation courses should be arranged for students of ignorant parents and they must be guided according to their mental level, so that may select the right career andbe able to avoid mal-adjustment and frustrations.
- There is need of reorganization and effective functioning and employment exchanges to facilitate the students towards job opportunities so that they may think for better career options.

- There should be encouragement towards job oriented courses such as constructive, technical and industrial. Such courses should be offered to the adolescents.
- It was observed from the result that family climate and career attitude and career competence are significant to each other, so administrators and teachers of schools should organize activities like seminars, workshops, lectures from guest speakers for the adolescents, to motivate them to participate actively in selecting their career.

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